

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ACHIEVING EQUIVALENCE IN SIMULTANEOUS AND WRITTEN TRANSLATION

Qodirova Nodira Baxram qizi

Uzbekistan State University of World Languages postgraduate student
nadiraxanim92@gmail.com

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Annotation. This article discusses the most common strategies for simultaneous and written translation. The article discusses the importance of equivalence in translation. The article also provides a comparative analysis of some units, examples of the equivalents of some words in Uzbek and English.

Key words: equivalence, simultaneous translation, translation, analysis, communication.

Аннотация. Ushbu maqolada eng keng tarqalgan sinxron va yozma tarjima strategiyalari muhokama qilinadi. Maqolada tarjimada ekvivalentlikning ahamiyati haqida soʻz yuritiladi. Shuningdek, maqolada ayrim birliklarning qiyosiy tahlili, oʻzbek va ingliz tillaridagi ayrim soʻzlarning ekvivalentlari misollar bilan berilgan.

Калит сўзлар: эквивалентлик, синхрон таржима, ёзма таржима, анализ, muloqot

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматриваются наиболее распространенные стратегии синхронного и письменного перевода. В статье обсуждается важность эквивалентности в переводе. В статье также приводится сравнительный анализ некоторых единиц, примеры эквивалентов некоторых слов в узбекском и английском языках.

Ключевые слова: эквивалентность, синхронный перевод, письменный перевод, анализ, коммуникация

Foreign language study is all about learning how to truly communicate and connect with others—an incredibly important life skill. Furthermore, in learning new language one should be able to translate the units in the second language correctly and appropriately. There are two strategies of translation: synchronous and written. Translation equivalence as a key issue in translation studies. There are three main approaches to translation equivalence; 1. Linguistic approach (Vinay, Darbelnet, Catford), 2. Semiotic approach (Jakobson) and 3. Middle ground (Nida, Baker, Ivir, House). The linguistic approach to translation focuses on the key issues of meaning, equivalence and shift. This procedure can maintain the stylistic impact of the SL text in the TL text. (Hatim, Munday, 2004.) In the semiotic approach, the TLR decodes the ST message first

and then has to transmit it into an equivalent message for the TC. This means that from a grammatical point of view languages may differ from one another to a greater or lesser degree, but this does not mean that a translation cannot be possible; in other words, the TLR may face the problem of not finding a translation equivalent (Jakobson,1959).

Synchronous translation is one of the most advanced types of translation in terms of complexity. In addition to translating what you hear and translate it at the same time, listening to the speaker's next speech requires a translator to be proficient and strong minded. Written translation strategies involve the basic tasks of choosing the foreign text to be translated and developing a method to translate it. Both of these tasks are determined by various factors: cultural, economic, political. It is important to figure out the most suitable translation of the word in both strategies.

Interpreting is a special type of communicative interaction which takes place when members of different language communities engage in cross-language/culture communication. The role of an interpreter becomes more crucial because as a good interpretation can be useful, a bad or a wrong one can be misleading and to some extent dangerous. Thus, interpretation from one language to another cannot be done adequately without knowledge of achieving equivalence in the languages.

Translation is one of the oldest types of human activity, a complex and multifaceted process. It is common to talk about "translating from one language to another", but in fact the process of translation is not only about replacing one language with another. Translating was seen as a decision-making process, where a translator often has different kinds of possibilities to choose in order to fulfil the function of the translation. If a particular language unit in one language carries the same intended meaning/message encoded in a particular language environment in another, then the two units are considered equivalent. The area of equivalents covers linguistic units such as morphemes, words, phrases, sentences, idioms and proverbs. So, the search for equivalents is the most problematic stage of translation. It should be noted, however, that this does not mean that the translator must always find one-to-one categorically or structurally equivalent units in two languages, that is, sometimes two different language units in different languages have the same function.

A. V. Koller names 5 factors that determine certain conditions for achieving equivalence:

1. Conceptual content conveyed by the text and focus on national equality.

2. Text-to-text translations due to stylistic, sociological, geographic factors and equivalent-oriented equivalents.
3. Text and language norms and text equations
4. Translation "Set up" - should be a pragmatic equivalent.
5. Some aesthetic, formal and individual features of the text - focus on the formal aesthetic equivalent.

Examples of Equivalents in English & Uzbek

The word **"bird"** may be equal to Uzbek quyon (rabbit) symbolically :
she killed two birds with one stone. = Ikkita quyonni bir o'q bilan urdi

"Shoulder" in English may equal bo'yin (neck) in Uzbek:

The blame rests on my shoulders. = ayb mening bo'ynimda.

"Bedsheet" in English may equal qor (snow) in Uzbek:

as white as bedsheet = qordek oppoq

"Gold" in English may equal toza (pure): heart of gold = qalbi toza.

"Thread" in English may equal qil (hair) in Uzbek:

His life hangs by a thread. = Uning hayoti qil ustida.

The **"number 9"** in English may equal the number **"7"** yetti (seven) in Uzbek:

She is on cloud nine= U yettinchi osmonda

Sometimes it is difficult for translators to translate some sentences from English into Uzbek as both languages have different tense structures. For example:

I wish I had a car = Qani edi mashinam bor bo'lsa

Some definitions of translation actually replace equivalence with identification and emphasize the need to fully preserve the content of the original in the translation. For example, when Fedorov uses the term "utility" instead of "equivalence", this utility implies "a complete transfer of the semantic content of the original."

However, this thesis has not found its confirmation in the observed evidence, and its supporters are forced to make many remarks that contradict the original definition. Thus, L.S. Barkhudarov's invariance "can be said only in a relative sense", "translation losses are inevitable; there is an incomplete transmission of the meanings expressed in the original text. but it remains unclear how this should be combined with the fact that "the immutability of the content plan" is expressed as a single determinant. According to Susanna Nykyri "Languages and cultures are considered to consist of several subsets. Words are also viewed as (potentially) having different kinds of meanings."

In conclusion, using translation strategies, finding appropriate equivalence has many advantages. When a word or phrase means exactly the same thing in both

languages, we call that an equivalence, and it's understandably one of the first things professional translators look for. Comparative studies of languages show that the translations of the words may not always be suitable when it is done by computer. In theoretical computer science and formal language theory, the equivalence problem is the question of determining, given two representations of formal languages, whether they denote the same formal language. So this requires a deep understanding of both cultures, not just the language.

References:

1. Barkhudarov L.S. Language and translation: Problems of general and special theory of translation. M.: Mejdunar. relation 1975.240s.
2. Essays by Galperin I.R. Stylistics of the English language. M.: Literary publishing house Foreign Languages... 1958. 459 p.
3. Komissarov V.N. General theory of translation. Guide. M.: CheRo. 2000.136s.
4. Komissarov VN Theory of translation (linguistic aspects). M.: secondary school... 1990. 253 p.
5. Susanna Nykyri "Equivalence and translation strategies in multilingual Theasaurus construction"Published by Åbo Akademi University Press Biskopsgatan 13, FI-20500 ÅBO, Finland 2010. 23-24p

